

Open Source and Service Repository Policy

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1.0¹

¹

This policy document reflects the status on the indicated date. The policy is expected to be subject to change, however, at most on an annual basis.

The OSSR mission

The ESCAPE Open-source Scientific Software and Service Repository (OSSR) is a sustainable open-access repository to share scientific software and services to the science community and enable high-quality open science. It hosts scientific software and services for data processing and analysis in astro-, particle and astroparticle physics, as well as test data sets, user-support documentation, tutorials, presentations and training activities.

The OSSR will enable a true multi-messenger data-driven cooperative approach based on the [FAIR principle requirements](#) and will become part of the EOSC global catalogue of services. In a collaborative effort of all ESCAPE partners, common and innovative approaches will be fostered.

The software, science tools and other services available in the ESCAPE OSSR are openly available to all and allow users to access multi-messenger and multi-domain software to mine open-access datasets. This guarantees cross-fertilisation and an open innovation environment for science interoperability and software re-usage.

Guidelines and rules of participation to the ESCAPE OSSR

Application of the policy

The following guidelines, agreed within the ESCAPE WP3 and gathered in the ESCAPE deliverable 3.7 - “License, provenance and metadata guidelines for the software and service repository”, indicate how to provide software to the OSSR and under which conditions, in particular regarding licensing and provenance. Integration of a new entry in the OSSR is subject to a curation phase that will validate its compliance with the guidelines below.

These guidelines are part of this OSSR policy and are therefore subject to change, following the entire policy’s update schedule - i.e. at most on an annual basis. An update may include changes in the required metadata. Repository contributors will be required to acknowledge and adjust entries under their responsibility to required changes within half a year after notification. Outdated or inadequate entries may be removed from the repository. The policy will next be adjusted by the end of the ESCAPE project.

Guidelines and rules of participation

As the ESCAPE OSSR is built on Zenodo, [its policies](#) apply.

In addition, the following requirements must be fulfilled:

1. Any digital resource provided into the OSSR **must contain a license**.
 - It must provide a machine-readable description of the license.
 - The application of the FAIR principles to the products offered in the OSSR results in the necessity to assign licenses to all relevant parts, including software code, containerized and bundled software and metadata.

2. It is **strongly recommended** to provide an open-source license. The choice of a **permissive open-source license is advised**.
 - The Terms of Use for the OSSR require contributors/providers to ensure that all copyright is respected when offering software products through the OSSR. Thus, compatibility between the licenses of derivative or combined works must be checked before the on-boarding into the OSSR and done by the contributor/provider.
 - The choice of proprietary licenses must be justified.
 - If the digital resource is still unlicensed, it is recommended to choose either the [MIT](#) or [BSD-3 Clause](#) license.
 - The metadata file itself is considered to be offered under a [Creative Commons CCO license](#).
 - For contributed software, [guidelines](#) are collected and offered to the contributors to manage the licenses in their software product.
 - Final ESCAPE open science products, as well as container images, are expected to follow these guidelines too.

3. It is **strongly recommended** that any software provided to the OSSR incorporates a **metadata file** that describes the software to be uploaded. The use of the CodeMeta project schema, and therefore the addition of a `codemeta.json` metadata file into the root directory of the resource is recommended for the OSSR.
 - The metadata file can be generated at using the [CodeMeta generator](#).
 - The minimum metadata information to be added into any digital resource is the one required to create a new upload or a new version within Zenodo. The strong recommendation is to create a metadata file which is as complete as possible.
 - In relation to the previous point, it is recommended to provide a summary of user-visible changes between versions (e.g. provide 'release notes' with every new software release as well as fill this field within the `codemeta.json`) together with the OSSR software product or its documentation. This is essential provenance information and helps fulfilling the FAIR principles.
 - It is the software provider's responsibility to verify that the entry contains the minimum provenance information defined in this document.
 - To date, the only ZenodoCI compatible metadata context file is the `codemeta.json` schema file.
 - Providing a `codemeta.json` file with the software, together with the use of the ZenodoCI will allow the provider to define all software metadata using a single model and implementation. The integration of the software into the OSSR, as well as the use of other services (such as the production of a container for the software) will be based on this metadata.

Process Overview

Why and What to Onboard?

Digital resources that can be onboarded into the OSSR include scientific software, limited size public datasets (as per [Zenodo limits](#)), container images, or repositories with full analysis environments. Submission to the OSSR catalog can be achieved by completing the OSSR onboarding process described in this policy and compliance with the [requirements](#).

Who is Involved?

- **Onboarder:** The author or maintainer of the software that is onboarded to the OSSR. The author/maintainer's contact details must be provided and a [Zenodo account](#) is required.
- **Onboarding manager:** The project that is submitted for onboarding can be allocated to a member of the OSSR project depending on the scientific community the project targets. The onboarding manager will act as contact for the onboarding procedure.
- **Reviewer:** A reviewer from the OSSR project will verify that the contribution meets the requirements and publish it to the OSSR.

What Needs to be Done?

- **Registering the contribution** for the onboarding process using the [registration form](#) and provide contact details there.
- **Following the checklists** provided by the onboarding manager.
- **Applying for publication** by registering the contribution to the OSSR community on Zenodo. After a positive check by the reviewer, the contribution will be added to the OSSR.

Step-by-step

1. Registration

- The onboarding procedure is started by **registering the contribution** in the [registration form](#). It is required to sign the [terms of use](#) to the OSSR.
- After filling the form, the onboarding manager will contact the submitter via the supplied contact details.
- The onboarding manager creates a ticket on the [ESCAPE project platform](#) to follow the onboarding process. The ticket for the onboarding process provides the steps in the onboarding process, is managed by the onboarding manager and can be viewed in the [template](#).

2. ESCAPE Members: Introducing the Software

As part of the onboarding, a short presentation should be held during a Focus Group 1 call using [this template](#). An example presentation can be found in [this talk](#).

A date can be booked [in this poll](#). The onboarding manager will schedule the presentation and add it to Indico.

If the software is not documented/has no documentation, a technical report should be filed using [this template](#); an example can be found at [this tech report](#). The report should be submitted to the onboarding manager.

3. Adapting Your Contribution

For a full description of requirements to your software, see the [software check list](#).

4. Publishing to Zenodo

The contribution can be uploaded to Zenodo either from its repository or manually, see this [tutorial](#).

- Make sure the Zenodo metadata matches the `codemeta.json` data.
- Check out [eossr](#) and how to automate the upload to the OSSR.

5. Review Process

The request to add the contribution to the OSSR will be checked for compliance with the requirements. The curation process can be followed and commented on in the corresponding merge request on the OSSR [curation platform](#).

- A matching onboarding ticket has to exist on the ESCAPE project platform. If it does not exist, the request will be rejected immediately.
- The validity of the `codemeta.json` is automatically checked.
- Compliance with the [software check list](#) is confirmed by the reviewer.

After final confirmation by the reviewer, the contribution will be added to the OSSR and is from that moment on also findable from the OSSR interface. Through the OSSR, the contribution will also be made available in aggregator sites like the EOSC portal.

In case of non-compliance with the rules and regulations of onboarded contributions, entries may also be removed after notification and lack of required changes after half a year.

Appendix

Checklist for Software

All points below are required, unless marked as “optional”. Please consider fulfilling the optional points; these usually provide benefit to the repository users.

Software Package Checklist

The contribution should meet the following standards:

- It is published as a stable versioned release of the project.
- It is released under an open-source license.
- Follow a reasonable set of software development / software engineering practices, see for example [presentations at the WOSSL workshop](#), [Research Software Engineers](#), or [the Netherlands eScience Center Guide](#).
- Consider providing a [container image](#) (optional).
- It is essential that a `codemeta.json` text file meeting the OSSR requirements is provided in or alongside the contribution on Zenodo.
- Create and check the `codemeta.json` file:
 - Check the [codemeta.json docs here](#).
 - Check our [eossr documentation](#) for details.
- Provide a pointer to the version control development platform in the `codemeta.json` file (e.g. GitHub, GitLab...)

Metadata definition

Property	Type	Description	OSSR Requirement Level
codeRepository	URL	Link to the repository where the un-compiled, human readable code and related code is located (SVN, github, CodePlex).	recommended
programmingLanguage	ComputerLanguage or Text	The computer programming language.	
runtimePlatform	Text	Runtime platform or script interpreter dependencies (Example - Java v1, Python2.3, .Net Framework 3.0). Supersedes runtime.	
targetProduct	SoftwareApplication	Target Operating System / Product to which the code applies. If applies to several versions, just the product name can be used.	
applicationCategory	Text or URL	Type of software application, e.g. 'Game, Multimedia'.	
applicationSubCategory	Text or URL	Subcategory of the application, e.g. 'Arcade Game'.	
downloadUrl	URL	If the file can be downloaded, URL to download the binary.	
fileSize	Text	Size of the application / package (e.g. 18MB). In the absence of a unit (MB, KB etc.), KB will be assumed.	
installUrl	URL	URL at which the app may be installed, if different from the URL of the item.	
memoryRequirements	Text or URL	Minimum memory requirements.	recommended
operatingSystem	Text	Operating systems supported (Windows 7, OSX 10.6, Android 1.6).	
permissions	Text	Permission(s) required to run the app (for example, a mobile app may require full internet access or may run only on wifi).	
processorRequirements	Text	Processor architecture required to run the application (e.g. IA64).	recommended
releaseNotes	Text or URL	Description of what changed in this version.	recommended
softwareHelp	CreativeWork	Software application help.	
softwareRequirements	SoftwareSourceCode	Required software dependencies	
softwareVersion	Text	Version of the software instance.	required
storageRequirements	Text or URL	Storage requirements (free space required).	recommended
supportingData	DataFeed	Supporting data for a SoftwareApplication.	
author	Organization or	The author of this content or rating. Please	required

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	Person	note that author is special in that HTML 5 provides a special mechanism for indicating authorship via the rel tag. That is equivalent to this and may be used interchangeably.	
citation	CreativeWork or URL	A citation or reference to another creative work, such as another publication, web page, scholarly article, etc.	
contributor	Organization or Person	A secondary contributor to the CreativeWork or Event.	
copyrightHolder	Organization or Person	The party holding the legal copyright to the CreativeWork.	recommended
copyrightYear	Number	The year during which the claimed copyright for the CreativeWork was first asserted.	
dateCreated	Date or DateTime	The date on which the CreativeWork was created or the item was added to a DataFeed.	
dateModified	Date or DateTime	The date on which the CreativeWork was most recently modified or when the item's entry was modified within a DataFeed.	
datePublished	Date	Date of first broadcast/publication.	required
editor	Person	Specifies the Person who edited the CreativeWork.	
encoding	MediaObject	A media object that encodes this CreativeWork. This property is a synonym for associatedMedia. Supersedes encodings.	
fileFormat	Text or URL	Media type, typically MIME format (see IANA site) of the content e.g. application/zip of a SoftwareApplication binary. In cases where a CreativeWork has several media type representations, 'encoding' can be used to indicate each MediaObject alongside particular fileFormat information. Unregistered or niche file formats can be indicated instead via the most appropriate URL, e.g. defining Web page or a Wikipedia entry.	
funder	Organization or Person	A person or organization that supports (sponsors) something through some kind of ficial contribution.	recommended
keywords	Text	Keywords or tags used to describe this content. Multiple entries in a keywords list are typically delimited by commas.	recommended
license	CreativeWork or URL	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.	required
producer	Organization or Person	The person or organization who produced the work (e.g. music album, movie, tv/radio series etc.).	

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provider	Organization or Person	The service provider, service operator, or service performer; the goods producer. Another party (a seller) may offer those services or goods on behalf of the provider. A provider may also serve as the seller. Supersedes carrier.	
publisher	Organization or Person	The publisher of the creative work.	
sponsor	Organization or Person	A person or organization that supports a thing through a pledge, promise, or fiscal contribution. e.g. a sponsor of a Medical Study or a corporate sponsor of an event.	
version	Number or Text	The version of the CreativeWork embodied by a specified resource.	
isAccessibleForFree	Boolean	A flag to signal that the publication is accessible for free.	
isPartOf	CreativeWork	Indicates a CreativeWork that this CreativeWork is (in some sense) part of. Reverse property hasPart	
hasPart	CreativeWork	Indicates a CreativeWork that is (in some sense) a part of this CreativeWork. Reverse property isPartOf	
position	Integer or Text	The position of an item in a series or sequence of items. (While schema.org considers this a property of CreativeWork, it is also the way to indicate ordering in any list (e.g. the Authors list). By default arrays are unordered in JSON-LD	
description	Text	A description of the item.	required
identifier	PropertyValue or URL	The identifier property represents any kind of identifier for any kind of Thing, such as ISBNs, GTIN codes, UUIDs etc. Schema.org provides dedicated properties for representing many of these, either as textual strings or as URL (URI) links. See background notes for more details.	recommended
name	Text	The name of the item (software, Organization)	required
sameAs	URL	URL of a reference Web page that unambiguously indicates the item's identity. E.g. the URL of the item's Wikipedia page, Wikidata entry, or official website.	
url	URL	URL of the item.	
relatedLink	URL	A link related to this object, e.g. related web pages	
givenName	Text	Given name. In the U.S., the first name of a	

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		Person. This can be used along with familyName instead of the name property	
familyName	Text	Family name. In the U.S., the last name of an Person. This can be used along with givenName instead of the name property.	
email	Text	Email address	
affiliation	Text	An organization that this person is affiliated with. For example, a school/university	
identifier	URL	URL identifier, ideally an ORCID ID for individuals, a FundRef ID for funders	
name	Text	The name of an Organization, or if separate given and family names cannot be resolved for a Person	
address	PostalAddress or Text	Physical address of the item.	
type	Object Type (from context or URI)	The object type (e.g. "Person", "Organization", "ScientificArticle", "SoftwareApplication", etc).	
id	URL	Primary identifier for an object. Must be a resolvable URL or a string used to refer to this node elsewhere in the same document	
softwareSuggestions	SoftwareSource-Code	Optional dependencies , e.g. for optional features, code development, etc	
maintainer	Person	Individual responsible for maintaining the software (usually includes an email contact address)	required
contIntegration	URL	link to continuous integration service	
buildInstructions	URL	link to installation instructions/documentation	
developmentStatus	Text	Description of development status, e.g. Active, inactive, suspended. See repostatus.org	
embargoDate	Date	Software may be embargoed from public access until a specified date (e.g. pending publication, 1 year from publication)	
funding	Text	Funding source (e.g. specific grant)	recommended
issueTracker	URL	link to software bug reporting or issue tracking system	recommended
referencePublication	ScholarlyArticle	An academic publication related to the software.	
readme	URL	link to software Readme file or documentation	required